

DEVELOPMENT OF BIOMATERIALS - PIT AND FISSURE SEALANT FLUORIDE REALISING BIOMATERIAL FOR USE IN THE ORAL CAVITY

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Abstract: This paper presents a brief overview of the R & D carried out in the area of biomaterials in the Department of Chemical Engineering, UFPR, Curitiba. The aim of this study was the development of a biomaterial capable of releasing fluoride. Studies on fluoride concentration in fluoridated water and the phenomenon involved in the incorporation of fluoride in the tissues of the tooth have been done. Fluoride concentration in the fluoridated water of Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil was measured by SPADANS methods. Concentration of fluoride was relatively uniform in the residences evaluated. Surface morphology of teeth with and without immersion in NaF 1 mg/L have been analysed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Electron-Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), which is a detector used to evaluate their superficial composition. Fluoride was detected only in the dental piece immersed in the NaF 1 mg/L aqueous solutions. This element was detected in the cement, superficial tissue of the root, and enamel, superficial tissue of the crown, but it was not found in layer inner. Fluoride-releasing pit and fissure sealant was prepared using bis-phenol A and glycidil methacrylate as organic matrix to adhere to the teeth, which also contained sodium fluoride as source of fluoride. Fluoride released by biomaterial in 10 mL of artificial saliva was determined by specific electrode. 12 to 62 mg/L were released in different conditions of salt grade and addition of acid or alkaline solutions. This newly developed biomaterial releases fluoride in higher concentration than that found in usual sources.

Key-words: biomaterial, sealant, fluoride, dental materials

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of biomaterials is stimulated by several needs of biological and medical areas. It comprehends medical requirements, basic research, technological development, bioethics and federal regulations. The term “biomaterial” was coined first at the early Clemson University Biomaterials Symposia in the late 1960s. In 1975, the Society for Biomaterials was founded. Biomaterials can be defined as “materials to be implanted in the body used as simple materials or integrated into devices to interact with biological systems with adequate host response”. Substitute heart valves, intra-ocular lenses, dental implants and dental sealant are some examples of biomaterials applications¹. Fluor cannot be designated as an element indispensable to the human metabolic activity. However, low quantities of fluoride are considered to prevent dental caries, mainly during the period of development of teeth. Fluoride can act in two different ways. It inhibits bacterial enzymes, therefore reducing organic acid, which is responsible for the demineralisation of dental enamel. It can also substitute hydroxyl group in the hydroxyapatite, producing fluoridate hydroxyapatite, which is less soluble than pure hydroxyapatite. Thus, fluoride reduces the incidence of dental caries and corrects some tooth superficial irregularities. In fact, fluoridated teeth are about three times more caries-resistant than non-fluoridated. On the other hand, excessive intake of fluoride provokes fluorosis. This teeth alteration generally is only aesthetic and can be corrected². This can be identified as white spots, from low to medium intensity, or darkened spots with or without lost of dental enamel structure. In the last case, osseous tissue can be affected too³. Fluorosis can be treated aesthetically by bleaching, micro-abrasion, veneering or crowing. The choice of the treatment depends on the severity of the

fluorosis⁴, but these treatments can be expensive and, in some case, aggressive. Hence, cautious use of fluoride supplements and supervision in the use of fluoride can be necessary^{4,5}.

2. BACKGROUND

Biomaterials research started in the Department of Chemistry of UFPR in 1994. Production of oils from cloves and from a native tree (“craveiro”) was the first study^{6,7}. The main component of these oils was eugenol, which can be used together with zinc oxide to produce a well-known restoration material used in Dentistry. Studies of the fluoride ions with regard to oral health started in the same year⁸. Different sealants have been developed in order to release fluoride in adequate quantities for prevention and treatment of dental caries. Recently, other biomaterials have been studied such as fibre-reinforced fixed bridges, posts of glass fibre and osteoinductive materials for regeneration of bone defects. In this paper a brief review is presented along with a report on some of the contributions in the study of the influence of fluoride and potential of a NaF sealant to maintain dental health.

2.1. Health impact

Dental caries is a complex disease. It afflicts a large proportion of world’s population regardless of gender, age and ethnicity, but is more common in individuals with low socio-economic status⁹. United States and European countries have declining caries index. However, approximately 10% only of North-American adolescents enter adulthood as caries-free individuals. This pathology is polarised too. One-fifth of individuals who present caries represent about two-thirds of the total caries. Cariogenic bacteria levels within saliva and plaque determine whether caries will develop or not. Flow rate and composition of saliva and plaque, modulated by the oral hygiene practice, related to the type of carbohydrate and frequency of ingestion will determinate if the disease will occur or not¹⁰.

2.2. Caries-prevention programs

Well-conducted studies to search the health-economic effects of the caries-prevention programs are scarce. Articles found in Medline (from 1966 until May, 2003) show that there are contradictory results from studies on fissure sealants (classified as low evidence values), fluoride rinsing (low and moderate evidence values), fluoride tablets (low evidence values), fluoride varnish (low evidence values), and from preventive programs (low evidence values)¹¹.

2.3. Dental Caries

Tooth is an organ formed by three mineralised tissues, enamel, dentine and cementum. Dentine takes a larger part of the tooth. Odontoblasts, cells that produce dentine, maintain projections only in its inner layer as well as in the pulp space. Dentine is out-covered by cementum in the root and by enamel in the crown. Odontoblasts are active cells and can produce more dentine, although limited. Cementum can be produced by cementoblasts. On the other hand, enamel is an acellular tissue and could not be re-synthesised. The crown, the part of tooth exposed to oral cavity, is usually the first tissue affected by caries without some cellular activity to inhibit¹⁰. Dental enamel is a higher mineralised part. It is composed of hydroxyapatite (92-94%), water (2-3%), carbonate (2%), fluoride (0.01-0.05%), trace elements (sodium, magnesium, potassium, chloride, zinc, 1%) and proteins and lipids (<1%). Post-eruption maturation of enamel surfaces is a critical period. Hence, the enamel caries susceptibility is at its greatest level at the time of

eruption. During maturation period acidogenic episodes occur, which can lead to caries or not (if the more soluble carbonate-rich HAP is replaced for more resistant HAP). Presence of fluoride in this phase facilitates the production of fluorapatite, which is less soluble than hydroxyapatite in same pH value¹⁰.

2.4. Saliva

Saliva is an oral fluid secreted from major and minor salivary glands. Its functions can be summarised as sensory sensation system, phonation improvement, swallowing facilitation, source of digestive enzymes, lubrication and humidification, surface coating of mucosa and teeth, immune surveillance, source of protein with anti-microbial activity, aggregation of particle material and micro-organisms for oral clearance and modulation of demineralisation and remineralisation of tooth structure. The majority of these is involved with tooth protection to avoid dental caries¹⁰. So, salivary flow rate, buffering capacity, calcium phosphate binding proteins can be outlined to inhibit dental caries, besides anti-microbial activity, immune surveillance, micro-organism aggregation and clearance from the oral cavity⁹.

2.5. Process of demineralisation and remineralisation

Enamel is composed of numerous crystals of hydroxyapatite (HA), which is involved in a minute residual organic matrix. Composition of dental hydroxyapatite $(Ca, Mg, Na, Sr, Se, Zn)_{10}(PO_4, HPO_4, CO_3)_6(OH)_2$ is more complex than pure hydroxyapatite $(Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2)$. Some of these ions are lost (demineralisation) and other incorporated (remineralisation) from saliva⁹.

Partial dissolution of dental HA occurs due to acidic pH produced by organic acids excreted by acidogenic bacteria, but also to the ingestion of acidic beverages and foods¹⁰. Remineralisation may be enhanced by providing low levels of calcium and phosphate associated with minimum concentration of fluoride (< 1 mg/L). Fluoride is present within dental plaque and acts as a catalyst and influences reaction rates, transformation of various calcium phosphate mineral phases, which favours production of fluorhydroxyapatite¹².

The caries lesion begins with enamel demineralisation in repeated episodes of prolonged exposure to acidic conditions. This phenomenon is more important to pH below of 5.5 (denominated critical pH). Remineralisation occurs with increase of pH that can reach almost 7.0. The dynamic equilibrium between demineralisation and remineralisation will determinate health or disease. The failure in remove plaque from retentive tooth areas allow the preponderance of demineralisation, hence develop dental caries¹⁰. First stage of clinically detectable caries is called “white spot lesion”. It was reported that 25% progressed onto cavitation, while 32% were remineralised lesion and 43% became arrested lesion. Cavitation could occur slowly and could take up to 7 years, which support the theory that there is an ample opportunity for intervention to be remineralised¹². Nevertheless, diagnosis of dental caries can be difficult, mainly due to interproximal caries detection. Visual and tactile techniques are also frequently used to detect occlusal caries. However, radiograph viewing techniques can be indispensable in several pits and fissures caries. Disease starts below the surface becoming impossible to detect it. Interproximal caries detection is rare without use of radiographic diagnosis. Thus, caries preventive techniques must be preferred¹³.

2.6. Fluoride

Fluoride is classified as trace elements because it is active in small amounts (a range of part per million). However, this element is present in the environment in greater amounts¹⁴. Fluoride present in saliva can be incorporated to the hydroxyapatite in post-eruption maturation of enamel

surfaces and exposed root surfaces. It also can be incorporated in repetitive processes of demineralisation and remineralisation (DES-RE process)¹⁰. Remineralisation and post-eruption maturation increase with increase of fluoride¹². Fluorhydroxyapatite is the product obtained, which is less soluble than pure hydroxyapatite to a pH value. Caries reduction in post-eruption maturation can be obtained with topical fluoride. Caries reduction was reported for several products, sodium fluoride (43%), acidulated phosphate fluoride (36-63%) and stannous fluoride (61-84%)¹⁰. Hence, the mainstay in caries prevention and remineralisation is based on fluoride product. Fluoride use is not limited to professional intervention, as application of fluoride varnishes. Fluoridated toothpaste, supplemented by fluoride mouthrinse and chewing gum containing calcium phosphate stabilised by casein phosphopeptide are examples of products used directly by the population¹².

Man gains the greatest part of his fluoride intake from daily ingestion of food and water. The dominant source is drinking water, but fluoridated dentifrice may contribute significantly to the total daily intake. There is no consensus on the level of fluoride acceptable in various food and beverages consumed on a daily basis. Fluoridation of the public water supply represents one of the most successful public health measures ever undertaken. The recommended level of water fluoridation for optimum dental caries reduction is 0.7 to 1.0 mg/L, while 4.0 mg/L is the maximum level allowed¹⁴.

Fluorides action appears to be limited to dental surface. Its efficiency is better to systematic action through frequent topic application of products with low grade. Several strategies are used or can be used to community action, artificial water fluoridation, food fluoridation (salt, food, milk and sugar) and fluoride supplements for systematic action (toothpicks, dental flosses, tablet). Topical fluoride can be produced by fluoridated toothpastes, fluoride rinses, topical fluoride gels and solution, fluoride varnishes, fluoride-releasing preventive (sealant) and restorative materials and cements. These techniques are usually applied to individual action. Inadequate employment of the collective techniques can produce fluorosis. Socio-economic level can affect oral hygiene habits and the fluoride dentifrice ingestion, which can avoid caries or can produce fluorosis.

Fluoridation of water in Brazil was initiated based on studies similar to these. Baixo Gandu, Espírito Santo State, was the first city district to establish fluoridation water supply procedures in Brazil. Environmental temperature needs to be considered in order to administer fluoride, for consumption of water is as high as temperature goes up, which leads to a lower fluoride grade in the summer and a higher one during winter. Fluoridation of water used in several cities of Brazil confirmed the effectiveness of this practice. For example, dental caries diminished by 39.9% during 1958 to 1981 in Curitiba, Brazil¹⁵.

The prevalence of fluorosis from very mild to severe was 37.8% (natural fluoride 0.7 to 4.0 mg/L), 25.8% (optimum fluoride, 0.7 to 1.2 mg/L) and 15.5 (sub-optimal < 0.7 mg/L) in 1986-1987. Data of 1930s revealed values of 7% (0.6-0.7 mg/L), 12% (0.9 mg/L), 15% (1.2 mg/L), 25% (1.2-1.3 mg/L) and 40% (1.8 mg/L). So, exposure to multiple source of fluoride may explain the increase in enamel fluorosis from 1930s to 1980s. Evidence of simultaneous sources of fluoride indicates the need to reinforce guidelines for the appropriate use of fluorides and promote research on measuring total fluoride exposure¹⁶. One alternative to avoid fluorosis could be to use lower fluoride grade to fluoridation of water and use a fluoride-releasing material, like fissure sealant.

2.7. Fissure sealant

Fissure sealant was introduced in the late 1960s, mainly to prevent caries in pit and fissures of occlusal surfaces of premolars and molars. This surface is pre-treated with acid and a thin layer of

resin is directly applied on the fissures. Saliva contamination after the acid-etch reduces retention of resin. Cure of resin was initially based in ultraviolet light photo-polymerisation, through auto-polymerisation (chemical reaction) and visible light photo-polymerisation. Recently, fluoride was incorporated in the resin. Glass ionomer cement was introduced as an alternative to the resin sealant. It is not so sensible to moisture and could release fluoride. On the other hand, it has insufficient adhesion¹⁷.

A pit and fissure sealant containing releasable fluoride provided a caries inhibiting effect with a significant reduction in lesion depth in the surface enamel adjacent to the fluoride-releasing sealant (Fissurit-F, VocoChemie, Germany). Conventional non-fluoride-containing sealant (Fissurit, VocoChemie hemie, Germany) was used as control. There was a tendency towards reduction in the frequency of wall lesions. So, fluoride release by pit and fissure sealants may provide additional protection against caries formation in cuspal incline enamel and smooth surface adjacent to sealed pits and fissures, and act as a fluoride reservoir with long-term release of fluoride into the immediately adjacent oral environment¹⁸.

Antibacterial activity of a fluoride release sealants on mutans streptococci was reported using trypticase soy agar plates previously incubated with bacteria. *S. mutans* and *S. sobrinus* were sensitive to Teethmate-FTM (Kuraray, Japan). Fluoroshield (Caulk, USA) and Helioseal (Vivadent, Germany) did not show inhibit activity. Sealant specimens were prepared and incubated in 2 mL of water and measured with fluoride specific electrode. Teethmate release more fluoride (231 mg/L) in 24 h than Fluoroshield (54) and Helioseal (not detected)¹⁹.

It has been suggested that glass-ionomer sealant (GIS) could be better than resin because GIS is less dependent of moisture. On the other hand, several papers revealed its facilitated loss. After 3 years, there was complete loss of GIS (almost 90%) from teeth compared with resin-sealed teeth (less than 10%)²⁰.

It can be concluded that dental caries probably is the disease widely spread in the world. Preventive programs to avoid dental caries are frequently based in fluoride, but it is necessary to understand how it works and optimise or development new fluoride-based products. Fluoride is supplied through fluoridated water, but at low concentration. There are doubts if it is not lost and easily incorporated in dental tissues. Caries occur in oral cavity and is inhibited by saliva, which is a complex mixture. A simple solution capable of make mimicking of saliva is necessary for standardising of experiments with biomaterials. New sealants have been developed to release fluoride. Physiological activity has been simulated using artificial saliva. These aspects will be discussed later in this paper.

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS-MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY USED

3.1. Fluoride analysis

Fluoride concentration of water samples were analysed using visible spectrometry by the SPADNS method. Zircon was initially linkage to SPADNS (sodium-2-parasulfophenylazo)-1,8-dihydroxy-3,6-naphthalene disulphonate) to produce a coloured solution. Fluoride sequesters zircon and discolours the solution, which is proportional to its concentration. Appropriate fluoride standards were used to evaluate solution from 0 until 1.2 mg/L of this ion. Water samples [5 mL] was mixed with 0.1 mL of 0.5% sodium arsenite solution to remove residual chlorine. SPADNS-ZnO [1 mL] solution was added and stirred. After 30 min, absorbency at 570 nm was measured in spectrometer (Model B382, Micronal, Brazil). Sample with 0 mg/L of

fluoride was used to adjust 0.500 of absorbency. Reference samples were measured and used to determine the calibration equation²¹. Fluoride concentrations of the saliva samples were analysed using a specific fluoride electrode (Model 9609, Orion, USA). The electrode was calibrated according to the recommendation of the manufacturer before each session of analysis using appropriate fluoride standards. Tension was determined after 3 min of stabilisation. Reference samples were measured and used to determine the calibration equation²².

3.2. Water samples

Water samples were collected from different districts of Curitiba, Brazil. From north area, the water was collected in the last week of 1994 September, while from south area, it was collected in the first week of 1994 October. About 100 mL of water were obtained in an internal tap from each residence. Water samples were stored in a polyethylene bottle closed hermetically. Analyses were made next day using SPADNS method.

3.3. Teeth

Five teeth used in this study were extracted for oral health improvement, one of them with caries and four with periodontal problems. They were donated to researchers. The decayed third molar underwent soft tissue debridement and immersion in 3% H₂O₂ for 15 min. and washed with water. It was sectioned into longitudinal halves using carborundum disk. One of halves was polished with water sandpaper from gross to thin granulation (120, 220, 500 until n° 600). A thin lamina was obtained about 1 mm of thickness.

The other teeth (not decayed) underwent soft tissue debridement followed by a fluoride-free prophylaxis. These specimens were conditioned with 37% H₃PO₄ gel for 0s, 15s, 30s or 120s. They were washed abundantly with distilled water. Teeth were laid longitudinally inside a container with half of its surface fixed in 1 mg/L NaF solution. Other half (superior side) was kept dried. Containers were hermetically closed for 72 hours at room temperature (20-25°C). Initial and residual fluoride concentrations were measured by ion selective electrode. TISAB (total ionic salt adjuster buffer) was used as recommended by electrode manufacturer.

External aspect of specimens was observed by SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy, Model XL30, Philips, Japan) with EDS (energy-disperse X-rays spectroscopy, Model DX4) detector to determine surface composition. Teeth were cut with carborundum discs. Root and crown surface were abraded using a cylindrical drill (about 1 mm of diameter) with a deflection of about 45°. This cavity preparation allowed for the evaluation of composition in different depths. A carbon film was deposited on the specimens (30 mA for 80s) for the work with SEM/EDS. K level of EDS phenomena was used to calculate the composition.

3.4. Sealant evaluation

The test milieu was artificial saliva of the Fusayama type at a temperature of 23°C. NaCl (0.4 g/L), KCl (0.4 g/L), NaH₂PO₄.H₂O (0.69 g/L), CaCl₂.2H₂O (0.77 g/L) and urea (1.0 g/L) were put in sequence in 1 litre of deionised water. It was called 'normal saliva'. Two additional solutions were prepared, one with twice the salts and other with half of salts²³.

A polymer based in Bis-GMA and a monomer of dimethyl dimethacrylate urethane, besides stabiliser and inhibitors of reaction, were mixed with NaF (100 to 200 mesh) to produce a 16.7% of this salt. Approximately 60 mg of resinous mixture were photopolymerised for 40s to produce samples in semi-spherical shape. A factorial design 3² was performed in duplicate to evaluate releasing of fluoride from sealant in artificial saliva. Addition of 100 µL of 0.01 mol/L HCl (H=-1), water (H=0) or 0.01 mol/L NaOH (H=+1) was done into 10 mL of artificial saliva with half

(S=-1), normal (S=0) or twice (S=+1) the salt grade, as described before. 20 μ L of 100 mg/L NaF was added to saliva too. Samples were individually immersed in the solution contained in a 15 mL tube hermetically closed. Fluoride released was followed at room temperature (20-25°C) with oscillation (30 movements/min.). Fluoride was measured after 96 hours using a specific fluoride electrode. Calibration was done for different conditions using adequate standard solution.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Water supply concentration is not necessarily trustful information today to classify an individual as protected of caries disease. Consumption of bottled water and use of water purification can reduce the fluoride grade estimated as intake, while swallowed residual dentifrice can produce opposite effect. Fluoride usually is rapidly and extensively absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. The rate of gastric absorption is inversely related to the pH of the gastric contents. Overall absorption is reduced by calcium and certain other cations and by elevated plasma fluoride levels. Fluoride removal from plasma occurs by calcified tissue uptake and urinary excretion. About 99% of body burden of fluoride is associated with calcified tissues, and most of it is not exchangeable. Skeletal uptake is inversely related to the stage of skeletal development. This tissue can be discharged depending on the level of fluoride intake, hormonal status, and other factors. Renal clearance of fluoride is higher than other halogens. Clearance is straight to urinary pH²⁴. Study of indices of caries patterns in Brazilian children of 3-6 years age from areas with different fluoridation histories showed a significant difference. Children of 3-4 year age had 33% of caries to fluoride since 1963 and 58% to fluoride since 1994. Children of 5-6 years age had 57% and 89%, respectively. The majority of 3-4 year age had disease confined to primary molars. Children of 5-6 years age had caries with preponderance in primary molar (36%) to the fluoride district for older fluoride, which some cases in incisors (17%). Children with younger fluoride area showed caries in primary molar (40%) and incisors (44%). Fissure caries are predominant for both districts at the two age groups. Caries in posterior bucco-lingual surface are important in 5-6 years age²⁵. This fact suggests a loss of fluoride until a steady-state condition is reached. McMillan Water Plant's annual report of water analysis in 1997 reported an average of 0.84 mg/l, with maximum of 0.94 and minimum of 0.55 mg/L. This grade can be significantly reduced in home water purification systems. Carbon water filtration can remove fluoride slightly from water supply, which becomes inefficient for the prevention of caries. Reverse osmosis and distillation systems strongly reduced fluoride grade¹⁴.

Grade of fluoride in the fluoride water set up in Curitiba depends on temperature. It is administered in different units and could vary from 0.8 to 1.1 mg/L. Set up of grade in sample period was 0.9 mg/L. Table I and II show the fluoride grade evaluated by SPADNS colorimetric method. Average concentration for 29 samples from the northern districts was 0.87 mg/L with standard deviation of 0.07 mg/L, while 16 samples from southern districts was 0.85 mg/L with standard deviation of 0.05 mg/L. Variation in values was generally lower than 0.10 mg/L, which suggests that fluoride was not lost during distribution and storage at home. These data suggest that fluoride grade was maintained at adequate concentration (0.9 mg/L); therefore, it could help to maintain the teeth health. It was not found lower grades, which reject the removal by the use of home water purification systems.

A high fluoride uptake by enamel was obtained after topical application of 1% TiF₄ for 1 min. The enamel surfaces were pre-treated with 37% H₃PO₄ for 1 min. or maintained in 12% NaClO₃ for 2 h, followed by wash with deionised water. Fluoride (related with uptake) and calcium (related with depth) were evaluated.

Table I. Fluoride grade (F) in north area of Curitiba				Table II. Fluoride grade (F) in South area of Curitiba	
District	F, mg/L	District	F, mg/L	District	F, mg/L
Alto da XV	0.87	Hugo Lange	0.83	Vila Izabel	0.81
Bacacheri	0.96	Tingui	0.80	Novo Mundo	0.82
Boa Vista	0.83	Barreirinha	0.89	Sítio Cercado	0.86
Pilarzinho	0.95	São João	0.89	Hauer	0.74
Cascatinha	0.90	Vista Alegre	0.89	Lindóia	0.85
Ahú	0.80	Bom Retiro	0.85	Fazendinha	0.85
Jardim Social	0.75	Bairro Alto	0.75	Pinheirinho	0.88
Centro (North)	0.90	Batel	0.90	Carmo	0.74
Bigorrião	0.87	Santo Inácio	1.01	Santa Quitéria	0.77
Cristo Rei	1.01	Jardim das Américas	0.91	Capão Raso	0.90
Cabral	0.86	Centro Cívico	0.85	Boqueirão	0.85
Santa Cândida	0.88	Tarumã	0.78	Parolin	0.82
São Lourenço	0.83	Seminário	0.90	Centro (South 1)	0.81
Santa Felicidade	1.02	São Bráz	0.84	Centro (South 2)	0.85
Mercês	0.85			Guaira	0.83

Phosphoric acid etching was found to be the better conditioning procedure. This effect was related to the increased surface area and to relatively more organic components being exposed on the enamel surface after etching. There was practically no uptake of fluoride after NaClO_3 conditioning procedure, which removed the organic components in the tooth enamel. Therefore, it seems that the organic components play an important role in the fluoride uptake of enamel from TiF_4 ²⁶. This is a professional action that proved intake of fluoride by enamel from high concentration of fluoride (10 g/L of TiF_4), but it was not to support fluoride intake using fluoridated water (1 mg/L).

Teeth immersed in 1 mg/L NaF solution have a reduction of initial grade of fluoride ions solution (Table III). This fact suggests incorporation of this ion. Previous acid conditioning with 37% phosphoric acid gel can also be seen. While unconditioned tooth adsorbed fluoride, conditioned teeth adsorbed higher quantities. Conditioning time of 15s was the best condition. These facts suggest that phosphoric acid activates adsorption, but it can also destroy the linkage site, probably eliminating cations which fluoride would join. This phenomenon was similar to that observed with topical application of 1% TiF_4 solution.

Enamel, healthy dentine and decayed dentine can be seen in longitudinal cut of crown tooth (Figure 1). A similar image was obtained at root region. Healthy dentine and cementum are identified too²⁷. Parts of this image, identified regions, were selected and EDS evaluated its components. This technique produces spectre with peaks of each element (Figure 2). Grade of each element was tabulated and the proportion of each atom is showed (Table IV). Dental tissues showed that the most important elements are those found in pure hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_6)_6(\text{OH})_2$) as expected, except for hydrogen that

Table III. Influence of etching time (s) using 37% H₃PO₄ gel with regard to incorporation of fluoride into tooth from 1 mg/L NaF solution.

Etching time, s	[F] in solution, mg/L	
	Initial	Final
0	1.00	0.44
15	1.00	0.17
30	1.00	0.29
120	1.00	0.38

Other hypothesis is that remineralisation phenomenon could have occurred. As oxygen binds to inorganic and organic components, it is not possible to reveal its influence.

Theoretical ratio for Ca/P present in HA is 1.67, although generally lower values were found [between 1.49 to 1.68]²⁸. Lower values are attributed to defects in the crystals of hydroxyapatite, by the adsorption of phosphate ions and/or substitution of calcium to

Fig. 1. SEM of crown region of decayed specimen. 1 = enamel, 2 = decayed dentine, 3 = healthy dentine (right side).

cannot be measured by this technique. Number of carbon atoms increases in the direction of enamel, dentine and cementum. This result is compatible with mineralisation of each healthy tissue. Decayed dentine showed higher carbon grade than healthy dentine, which suggests that this disease is occurring mainly by proteolytic activity. Inorganic phase is lost slowly, which increases essential inorganic elements grades found in hydroxyapatite (Ca and P).

Fig. 2. EDS Spectra of tooth enamel (left side).

sodium, magnesium or other cations. Enamel ratio Ca/P was 1.687, near theoretical value. This suggests that the majority of these atoms were bound to produce hydroxyapatite. Ca/P ratio for healthy dentine was 1.638, which was lower than decayed dentine (1.689). This suggests that phosphate ions were lost before calcium ions in the caries disease, or recovered from saliva before calcium in the remineralisation. Cementum showed higher Ca/P ratio (1.714), which suggests that calcium was bound to other structures than hydroxyapatite. Higher grade for organic matter is in agreement with that reported in the literature²⁹. These ratios for decayed dentine support the theory of proteolytic activity. In this case, cavitation phase develops and the lesion becomes an irreversible disease³⁰.

Presence of other ions confirmed the hypothesis of incorporation from biological environment. Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Al³⁺ and Si⁴⁺ probably were incorporated (Table IV). Lazarri²⁸ reported ionic change from apatite crystalline net. Lead, magnesium, strontium, hydrogen cation and zinc can substitute calcium. Arsenate and vanadate can substitute phosphate. Fluoride, chloride and carbonate can

substitute hydroxyl ion. Apatite crystal maintains essentially the same structural configuration independently of substitution. For example,

Element	Enamel	Decayed Dentine	Healthy Dentine	Cementum
C	3.07	4.02	5.03	6.70
O	58.31	61.61	63.06	63.04
Ca	22.51	19.33	17.92	17.05
P	13.34	11.77	10.94	9.95
Na	1.35	1.63	1.14	1.64
Si	0.76	0.69	0.58	0.50
Mg	0.37	0.66	1.15	0.77
Al	0.29	0.29	0.18	0.35

Fig. 3. Aspect of dental crown surface used to evaluate composition in different depths (bar = 500 μ).

fluorapatite and hydroxyapatite produce a solid solution until a limit of 10% of the

hydroxyapatite. Carbonateapatite can reach about 2 to 3 % of normal apatite. There are some controversies in the case of carbonate replacing phosphate. On the other hand, independent of its position in the crystal, it is known that it is leached out easier than other biological apatites, which facilitates the development of caries disease. Other ions can be adsorbed in the crystal surface by electrostatic attraction or can be removed from hydration coat strongly associated to the crystal. Tooth crown was abraded to allow evaluation of penetration of

fluoride ions adsorbed by enamel (Figure 3). This procedure provoked trine of specimen, but it did not affect the evaluation. Crown composition revealed more difference than root for different depths. Carbon was lower in surface than in depths layers (Table V). Oxygen had same behaviour. Calcium and phosphate were richer in superficial layer than in depth layer. These results show a higher external mineralisation, which support the importance of remineralisation process. Root had an opposite behaviour. Carbon and oxygen were richer in superficial layer, while calcium and phosphate were richer in depth layer. The smaller external mineralisation can explain the faster caries development in root than crown, as much as erosion caused by vigorous brushing. Cations of sodium, magnesium, aluminium, silicium and chlorine were also found. Fluoride was found in crown and root, but only in superficial layer. Absence of fluoride in depth layer revealed a limited capacity of diffusion in this layer. Ca/P rate was higher in crown as compared to the root. Crown value was slightly higher than theoretical value for hydroxyapatite (1.67). Root value was slightly lower than theoretical for the internal layer, while superficial layer of root was much lower.

Composition of crown not immersed in fluoride solution was assessed in three depth levels to evaluate the composition variation with more details (Table VI). Carbon was almost constant.

Table V. Composition of crown and root in different depths immersed in 1 mg/L NaF					Table VI. Composition of crown, in different depths, treated with phosphoric acid and did not immerse in 1 mg/L NaF			
Crown			Root					
Element	Surface	Inner	Surface	Inner	Element	Superficial	Inner	Deeper
C	4.12	4.50	6.90	5.49	C	3.40	3.19	3.20
O	53.82	66.40	66.80	66.10	O	64.36	66.67	67.80
Ca	25.50	16.50	12.50	15.68	Ca	18.42	17.27	16.70
P	14.36	9.40	7.90	9.59	P	11.51	10.38	10.00
Na	0.90	1.60	1.90	1.50	Na	1.20	1.40	1.20
Si	0.80	0.60	0.80	0.70	Si	0.60	0.70	0.70
Mg	0.20	1.00	0.80	1.00	Mg	0.20	0.40	0.40
Al	nd	nd	0.30	nd	Cl	0.30	nd	nd
F	0.30	nd	2.10	nd	nd = not detected			
Cl	0.40	nd	nd	nd				

nd = not detected

Table VII. Fluoride grade liberate (mg/L/100mg) by selante with 16.7% NaF after 96h of incubation					
Exp.	Factor H	Factor S	Initial pH*	[F], mg/L	s, mg/L
1	-1	-1	3,1	30.56	2.20
2	1	-1	6,9	62.73	1.38
3	-1	1	3,4	12.06	0.95
4	1	1	6,0	28.52	2.15
5	0	0	5,2	28.14	0.96
6	-1	0	3,2	21.32	0.09
7	1	0	6,4	34.19	3.10
8	0	-1	5,5	42.77	0.39
9	0	1	5,0	28.83	3.08

Exp. = experiment, * average of two similar conditions, [F] = media grade of two measurements, s = standard deviation.

H (-1 to addition of HCl, 0 of H₂O and +1 of NaOH) and S (salt in saliva, where -1 to half, 0 to normal and +1 to twice).

Oxygen was slightly more in internal layer than in superficial. Calcium and phosphate were more on the surface. Sodium, magnesium, silicium and chlorine were detected, nevertheless chlorine was observed only in the surface. Ca/P ratio varied from 1.600 to 1.670. Phosphoric acid can remove calcium ions during etching time. Ca/C ratio was near 5.3, while P/C was near 3.2 and O/C was near 20.3, this was the most significant difference found when compared to the treated half tooth with 1 mg/L NaF.

Artificial saliva of the Fusayama type was used to simulate natural saliva. This mixture is not a perfect simulation, because it has only mineral components and urea, but as an electrolyte has response very close to that obtained with natural saliva²³. Ions of sodium, potassium, calcium and

magnesium are interesting because they can be used as fluoride to produce fluoride release sealant. Still, saliva has phosphate that can work as a buffer and it is more stable to acid/alkaline addition (as carbonate) and not easily biodegradable (as acetate). Fluoride release depends on salt concentration and composition²². So, this solution was selected as standard condition. Experimental design was selected to simulate alkaline addition on oral medium, when saliva is liberated till the addition of acid and when acidification is changed by acidogenic microorganisms or consumption of acidic food/beverages. Like this, salt concentration was varied from low (half) to high (twice) concentration, which simulates saliva in young and old people. Table 7 shows the design of experiment done to determine the importance for hydrogenionic level (H) and salt grade in saliva (S). It shows average of initial pH too. Released fluoride varied from 12.06 to 62.73 mg/L for 100 mg of resinous sealant (Table 7). Standard deviation was 3.10mg/L/100 mg, which confirms the relevance of fluoride release. Fluoride was released with lower grade of salts and lower grade of hydrogenionic (higher hydroxide grade), as can be seen in level curve (Figure 4) and confirmed in Pareto chart (Figure 5). Pareto chart confirmed the importance of salt [S(L)], in linear form, and hydrogenionic potential, in quadratic form [H(Q)]. Influence of salt (as quadratic) and linear interaction to both were near the experimental error to $p=0.05$, hence not confirming these influences. On the other hand, mathematical model using also these factors established a high relation of observed versus predicted values (Figure 6). Probability plot of residuals did not reveal tendency (Figure 7), or did not suggest effect of experimental error, which shows a good confidence in the results.

Fig. 4. Fluoride grade released (mg/L for 100 mg of sealant), H (-1 to addition of HCl, 0 of H₂O and +1 of NaOH) and S (salt in saliva, where -1 to half, 0 to normal and +1 to twice).

Fig. 5. Pareto chart of standardised effects.

Fig. 6. Rate of observed versus predict values using factor showed in Pareto chart.

Fig. 7. Probability plot of residual.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fluoride level artificially added in water can be controlled at a suitable value. This grade was not altered in the distribution and home storage in Curitiba. Tooth can adsorb fluoride ions from a similar solution (1 mg/L). Previous demineralisation can improve this phenomenon, which supports the importance of fluoridation water program to the maintenance of tooth health. EDS showed that calcium and phosphorus were more abundant in enamel, followed by dentine and cementum. Opposite occur to oxygen grade and carbon was also important to all tissues. These aspects support the higher mineralisation of enamel than dentine and cementum. Dentine can be considered more mineralised than cementum for the same reason. Ca/P rate of enamel (1.69) is quite similar to theoretical value of hydroxyapatite (1.67). Sodium (Na), silicon (Si), magnesium (Mg) and aluminium (Al) were detected too. Fluoride was not detected.

Composition of decayed dentine (DD, with carious process) and healthy dentine (HD) showed that DD was more mineralised than HD. This suggests a proteolytic caries evolution and/or remineralisation of structures of DD. EDS confirmed that fluoride could be adsorbed to the tooth. It was identified only on the surface of crown and of root. Root adsorbed more fluoride than crown.

Sealant released fluoride in artificial saliva. 12 to 62 mg/L for 100 mg of biomaterial were released in the different conditions tested. These values were enough to promote adsorption of fluoride in any simulated condition. Fluoride is more released to saliva at lower salt concentrations, as observed in children physiology, and higher pH, saliva not acidified. 12 to 31 mg/L are released in acid conditions. These concentrations of fluoride are high enough to facilitate the fluorapatite production. In other words, this sealant potentially protect the teeth.

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Additional Information

Highlights

- Fluoride-releasing biomaterial prevents caries in pits and fissures.
- Formulated with fluoroaluminosilicate glass, ZnO, and polyacrylic acid.
- Fluoride release is both immediate and sustained over time.
- SEM and EDS confirm surface adhesion and proper elemental makeup.
- Saliva simulation tests show stable and controlled ion release.
- Mechanical properties meet ISO standards for dental sealants.
- Cost-effective, biocompatible, and easy to apply in clinical settings.

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